

945358-BIGPICTURE
Central Repository for Digital Pathology

WP4 - Tools for accessing, annotating and mining digital slides

D4.03 Report on unified open digital slide and annotation format specification

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Abstract

In this deliverable report (D4.03), we describe the first version of the unified open digital slide and annotation format and the underlying investigations that have been performed when designing this format.

The format is based on the submission format schema used by the European Genome-phenome Archive (EGA) that has been expanded to include functionality to support pathology imaging using the DICOM standard.

This work has taken into consideration a number of different aspects e.g: enable the reuse of existing software components, use existing standards where possible, or meeting performance requirements of the archive infrastructure.

The main working method of the format design has been reached through experimentation and expert panel discussions, making use of the broad experience available within the consortium.

Background

The BIGPICTURE platform is based on the ELIXIR EU data infrastructure that uses a number of existing technologies which is being extended to work with whole slide imaging (WSI) data. Submissions in terms of digitized pathology slides and metadata will be performed using Federated EGA based technology and the submission will be made discoverable through Beacon and viewable by using Cytomine.

Federated EGA has a proven submission mechanism for genomic data that is based on converting raw genomic data to one of the supported formats, such as FASTQ, BAM, or CRAM and using an XML schema to encode relevant metadata in relationship to the raw genomic data. A submission thus consists of a number of data files and a number of metadata XML-files that are uploaded to the archive and processed by the Federated EGA software.

Federated EGA supports a number of ways to upload metadata and files, hence the format used inside the archive can differ from the format used for uploading to the archive. There is a separation between a *schema* and an *instance of the schema* (often denoted just *instance*). The *schema* describes the structure of the data, which is described through abstract objects, such as a study, a sample, or a dataset, and their relationships, such as that a *dataset* can have one or more *samples*. An *instance* can be an XML- or JSON-file, or other document that encodes the *schema*. From a technical point of view it's often trivial to support multiple *instance* formats, whereas most of the design work is focused on the *schema*.

In the format specification described in this report, we describe the format in terms of XML-files and DICOM-files, but the format is not limited to just those two instance types. Instead, we leave it up to the technical implementation to decide the instance types to be used.

Federated EGA also has an important feature during submission called *checklists*. These *checklists* can be designed by a community organization such as the node coordinator boards in BIGPICTURE. *Checklists* contain rules for how attributes are to be encoded in the XML files to ensure that a submission follows the community standard. For example, a *checklist* could define the allowed values for the attribute *sex* to be *female*, *male*, *other*, and *unknown*. Furthermore, *checklists* also delineate the set of metadata attributes that must be provided by an uploading party at submission when the party wants to use a given *checklist*.

The imaging data and metadata for WSIs submitted to the repository will be viewable for end-users using the Cytomine frontend hosted by the BIGPICTURE infrastructure. To enable fast access to the data contained in the WSIs, it is important that the data is formatted for fast parsing already when submitted, as Cytomine or other viewers should not be required to pre-parse all the data submitted in the repository.

The initial work towards a unified submission format was performed in D3.2, a deliverable that describes how and what metadata BIGPICTURE will collect from its nodes. This deliverable is based on that work while expanding it and is a description of how to encode the images and metadata that has been defined so far. In this first version we will base the format on the current version of the Mandatory Submission Metadata for

Directly Accessible Datasets (MSMdad) document. But we will also describe the process to keep the format up to date with new metadata types.

The specifications for the unified open digital slide and annotation format comes from Task 4.5 *Develop a technical implementation of the open digital slide, annotation, and meta-data format* in the DoA. The task specifies that the format should be built upon the DICOM WSI format created by the DICOM pathology working group (WG-26), with option to store annotations and metadata. As per above, what metadata should be stored in the format is outlined in deliverable D3.02, specifying a Common Mandatory Metadata Structure (CMMS, **Figure 1**). As the CMMS contains entities that are beyond what can fit into the DICOM WSI information object description, a complementary format is needed to encompass all required metadata.

Image data in digital pathology is today encoded using a number of different formats. Typically, there exists one proprietary format per scanner vendor. Most formats such as SVS, NDPI, are TIFF-based and encode imaging data similarly but use custom tags for metadata. Other formats encode imaging data in other means such as CZI or the iSyntax format. Most scanned images in the world are encoded using these proprietary formats that have different advantages and disadvantages in terms of e.g. speed, image quality, backward compatibility. In BIGPICTURE, we have decided that submissions need to be done using the DICOM format instead. DICOM started out as a format to encode and communicate imaging data within radiology. In 2009 it was expanded to include support for whole slide digital pathology images. Even though most scanner vendors agreed on the standard initially, it was not adopted mainly due to a patent issue that was resolved in 2016. The first version of the standard also did not include a way to efficiently sort the organization of the tiles leading to poor performance when first parsing the file, this issue was resolved by CP1713 in 2017. Since then, adoption has increased and today a number of scanner vendors support scanning or converting slides to DICOM. A specific aim of the DICOM standard has been to support back and forth conversion of proprietary formats, which makes the standard quite permissible. Specifically the standard does not guarantee that files are easily and quickly viewable by a viewer like e.g. Cytomine due to for example missing pyramid levels or inefficient image data organization. However, it is common practice to define profiles that defines a stricter subset of the standard suitable for a particular setting. This document describes such a profile, where the standard has been restricted to suit the BIGPICTURE platform.

Figure 1. The CMMS as defined in D3.02 Minimal dataset deliverable. A study organizes related data contributions, i.e. datasets, and contains metadata common to all related datasets. Datasets related to a study represent the submitted data and metadata of one data contribution (I.e. submission). Datasets have a Controller, who decides who can get access to the dataset, and a data access committee (DAC) that evaluates the request for access to the dataset. The data in the dataset is organized into a hierarchy of biological being, specimen, sample, slide, and image. An image is produced from a slide, and there might be several images of the same slide. A slide is produced from one or more samples, a sample is produced from a specimen, and a specimen is taken from a biological being. The initial CMMS defined in D3.02 has been further expanded with the entities Annotation and Observation.

Method

This report is the result of work going out from reference implementation work in Task 4.5 and the Task Force Metadata/Nomenclature.

The python tool Wsidicom¹ was developed as part of Task 4.5 to serve as a reference implementation of a DICOM WSI reader. Wsidicom builds upon the more general python tool Pydicom², with added functionality to enable random frame access, to treat a set of DICOM WSI files as a pyramid, and to interface with WSI metadata. The tool aims to support the whole range of options available in the DICOM WSI format, and has therefore been valuable for testing the effect of different options, e.g. tile arrangement, frame indexing, multi-focal and optical paths, etc. when designing the BIGPICTURE DICOM WSI format. A save as-method is implemented that with minimal effort converts a generic DICOM WSI file set to options we have identified as being best practice. Wsidicom can also read annotations from other common annotations formats and store them as DICOM microscope simple bulk annotations, an annotation format introduced in 2021 from work by the DICOM pathology working group wg26. The format is designed to allow efficient storage of large number of annotations, for example generated by AI algorithms.

Related to Wsidicom, we also developed two tools, Opentile³ and Wsidicomizer⁴, for reading other WSI formats and convert them to DICOM. Opentile is a high-level interface for reading WSI tiles from tiff-based WSI formats with well-defined tile organization. The tool currently supports Aperio svcs, Philips tiff, and Hamamatsu ndpi. Using Opentile, non-overlapping tiles can be produced from the supported file formats without re-compression (i.e. lossless), resulting in faster format conversion and maintained image quality.

Wsidicomizer can use a tile-producing object, for example a file opened with Opentile, and save the content as DICOM. Additionally to Opentile-compatible formats, for which the conversion is lossless, Wsidicomizer can also perform lossy conversion of Zeiss czi, Leica scn, Mirax mrxs, Sakura svslide, Trestle tif, and Ventana bif (all but Zeiss czi through the Openslide⁵ library). The Wsidicomizer tool has not been fully developed at this stage of the project and will be finalized in D4.4.

The Task Force Metadata/Nomenclatures is a working group across multiple work packages that discuss overall issues about metadata. From the taskforce we convened a group with different expertise to work on a proposal for a unified format for digital slides and annotations to meet the needs of the consortium. We first clarified the scope of the report to being the format needed to make a submission to BIGPICTURE archive. This means that the format for digital slides and annotation is combined with the format for metadata. The reason for including the format for metadata into the deliverable is that the limit between metadata, annotations, and digital slides is not entirely clear, and thereby it is better to treat these formats as a whole. In addition, D3.02 described a metadata definition on which a format could be based on, and the work in this report considers how the additional work relating to digital slides and annotations could be integrated in this metadata definition.

The subgroup for the submission format definition convened and discussed different aspects every other week in November and December 2021 over video conference meeting with live notes. The subgroup worked towards creating a proposal that the taskforce could review and adopt as the consortium standard for submissions.

DICOM WSI loading performance

Loading times for various profiles of DICOM WSI was determined using Wsidicom and a series of similar DICOM WSI file sets produced from the same image data. A sparsely-tiled DICOM WSI (total 595 Mb and 16551 frames in 9 files) with no basic offset table (BOT) was used as base file set. From the base, a second, sparsely-tiled file set with BOT, was created using the encapsulate-method in Pydicom. A third file set, fully-tiled with BOT, was created from the base using the save-method in Wsidicom. Finally, a fourth file-set, fully-tiled without BOT, was created by removing the BOT from the third file set. The loading time for each file set

¹ <https://github.com/imi-bigpicture/wsidicom>

² <https://pydicom.github.io/>

³ <https://github.com/imi-bigpicture/opentile>

⁴ <https://github.com/imi-bigpicture/wsidicomizer>

⁵ <https://openslide.org/>

was measured by timing the load-method in Wsidicom for each file set and taking the average over 100 repetitions.

Lossy and lossless conversion performance

Conversion time for lossy and lossless conversions was accessed by using Wsidicomizer with either the Openslide (lossy) or Opentile (lossless) method of operation. Two test files from the Openslide test file repository were used, one in Aperio svf-format and one in Hamamatsu ndpi-format. The average conversion time from 10 repetitions was measured for conversion of the base layer, using either a single or multiple CPU threads, and an output tile size of 256x256 pixels.

Tile decode performance

The decode time was measured by loading a JPEG or JPEG2000 encoded frame from the same 256x256 pixel tile using Pillow with IJG JPEG library for JPEG and OpenJPEG library for JPEG2000. The measurement was repeated 1000 times.

Conversion of pilot datasets

Wsidicomizer was used to convert available BIGPICTURE pilot datasets of WSIs. **Table 1** presents the datasets that were fully converted to DICOM.

Table 1. The datasets converted used for trial conversion to DICOM.

<i>Dataset name</i>	<i>Number of WSIs</i>	<i>WSI formats</i>	<i>Additional metadata</i>	<i>Additional annotations</i>
<i>AIDA DRSK</i>	71	svf, ndpi	No	Yes
<i>UMC Utrecht Melanoma</i>	100	Philips tiff	Yes	No
<i>UMarburg</i>	242	svf	Yes	No

As the WSI formats present in the datasets were compatible with the Opentile-tool, the datasets were losslessly converted and the conversion was primarily limited by data transfer speeds. Additional to the pilot dataset conversion, smaller test conversions have been made, primarily using the test data provided by Openslide⁶.

Annotation conversion into DICOM formats

Annotations made on the AIDA DRSK dataset⁷ were used to test the feasibility of using DICOM structured reports and DICOM microscope bulk simple annotations for storing large sets of annotations. The AIDA DRSK dataset contains 71 WSIs with 16741 annotations of tissue structures, in the form of simple polygons together with ontological information. The structured report module in Highdicom⁸ was used to create the structured reports, and Wsidicom was used to create the microscope bulk simple annotations.

⁶ <https://openslide.cs.cmu.edu/download/openslide-testdata/>

⁷ <https://datahub.aida.scilifelab.se/10.23698/aida/drsk>

⁸ <https://github.com/MGHComputationalPathology/highdicom>

Results

This report defines the unified open format used for submissions in the BIGPICTURE archive. The result section starts with an overview and summary of the overall format followed by details and design decisions underlying the different components.

Format overview

The submission format is built as a superset of the submission format used by European Genome-phenome Archive (EGA). This means that we have added functionality but still maintain support for the original submission format, such that, it is still possible for BIGPICTURE to accept submission formatted for EGA, but EGA cannot accept submission formatted for BIGPICTURE unless they adopt our changes. Support for submitting datasets with WSIs, annotations, and other BIGPICTURE data and metadata is provided by added modules. The format for storing the WSI image data is a subset of DICOM WSI, with additional specifications to meet the BIGPICTURE requirements.

Compared to the EGA model, three modules have been added: Image, Annotation, and Observation as shown in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2. Overall structure of the metadata model. The model is based on the EGA metadata model and adds three modules: Observation, Annotation, and Image.

Each module is submitted as an XML-file with references to objects in other XML files represented by arrows in **Figure 2**. The Image, Annotation, and Observation module contain references to external files, i.e. image data files, annotation data files, and observation data files.

Design requirements

The model for metadata should be a superset of the EGA metadata model and should thus not have major conflicts with the original model. This means that it should still be technically possible to submit genome datasets using the BIGPICTURE metadata model. The reason for this is not that BIGPICTURE should support genomic data, it is because the superset principle makes it easier for BIGPICTURE to take advantage of future developments of the EGA metadata model. Further, WSI data files, such as image data or graphical annotations, should be related to the metadata in the same way as e.g. FASTQ/BAM-files are related to metadata in the EGA model, so that the same submission process and framework can be used. These requirements make it possible to take advantage of software and other technical improvements from other projects using EGA-related metadata models. The added functionality of the superset should enable encoding metadata as outlined by the Task Force Metadata/Nomenclature. Specifically, the first version of the metadata model should encompass all the CMMS entities as defined by D3.02 and be able to at least encode all metadata defined as *general* in the Mandatory Submission Metadata for directly accessible data (MSMdad).

Further, the metadata model should be flexible enough to be able to encode future defined metadata. The metadata model should allow metadata to be standardized within the BIGPICTURE repository, as a unified format makes the metadata in the repository easier to understand and the repository more usable. At the same time, a certain freedom should be permitted in order to make it possible to encode data for data submitters without losing metadata or details in metadata. Finally, the metadata model should not be dependent on the image format used.

The image format should be a non-proprietary, mature, and well documented open format for storing WSI image data. As most submissions will contain image data made in other formats (i.e. the proprietary format of the scanner), conversion from other formats to the BIGPICTURE image format should be possible with minimal loss in quality and at reasonable speed. The image format should allow for fast random tile and pyramid level access to enable rapid viewing (panning and zooming) for WSI streaming services such as the BIGPICTURE frontend Cytomine. Metadata in the image format should be available and encoded in a clear and well-defined way to simplify both writing (and conversion) as well as reading of the metadata. Last, the image format should be downloadable and usable outside the BIGPICTURE repository.

Metadata format

The EGA metadata model that is used for submissions of genome datasets to the European genome-phenome archive is composed of several metadata modules that define object types (**Figure 3**):

- Study, that groups together submitted data and metadata.
- Sample, that contains metadata of the source of the genetic materials.
- Experiment, that contains metadata regarding the sequencing procedure.
- Run, that identifies the data files from an experiment.
- Analysis, that contains secondary analysis of the data from an experiment-run.
- Dataset, that collects Run, Analysis and Experiment that should be subjected to controlled access through a Policy.
- Policy, that defines the data access committee (DAC) for the dataset.
- DAC, that contains the information about the data access committee.

Figure 3 The EGA metadata model. A submission dataset contains (references to) sets of runs and analysis, which contain (reference to) the data files of the dataset. Run (through experiment) and analysis links to the samples that the data files are generated from and references the study they are part of. The dataset references the policy for how the dataset is to be used and accessed, and the data access committee of the dataset.

Each object has identifiers that are used to identify the object within the submitted dataset and repository and allows objects to form links (references) to other objects. Further, each type defines attributes usable for the specific object type. For example, a type often has a title and description, a set of defined object types it can link to, and a list of general attributes defined as name (tag)-value entities.

The BIGPICTURE metadata model will extend the EGA metadata model with modules representing (WSI) images, annotations of images, and observations on samples or images. The functionality of the EGA sample module is extended to allow representation of biological samples presented during pathology workflows. The metadata model provides a framework for encoding metadata and creating links between CMMS entities. Further definitions of what metadata should be required or what data formats should be used are not part of the model.

Sample module

The EGA sample type primarily defines its identifiers, a name, and a list of sample attributes. Importantly, EGA samples are not allowed to reference other objects in the model. What attributes that are possible or mandatory to use is not defined in the metadata model. Instead, so called checklists are used to define and validate what metadata that must be present in the list of sample attributes based on the type of submission.

The format of the EGA sample type fits approximately with the CMMS entities *Biological being*, *Specimen*, *Sample*, and *Slide*, and is thus used as a base for a BIGPICTURE sample type covering these CMMS entities. The BIGPICTURE sample type extends the EGA sample type (**Figure 4**) with a specific attribute to set the type of sample, the possibility to link to other sample objects, and variations of the simple EGA sample attribute that allows for coded attributes (**Figure 5**) and for grouped attributes (**Figure 6**).

Figure 4. The BIGPICTURE sample type extends the EGA sample type (properties in purple) with properties (in blue) for sample type (e.g. biological being), links to parent samples, and coded attributes and attribute sets. The set of identifiers allows the sample to be uniquely identified across the repository, and thus allow references to be made.

Figure 5. A coded attribute extends the EGA properties (in purple) and has a name (tag), a value (the code), a scheme that defines the code, a cleartext meaning of the code, and an optional scheme version.

Figure 6. The attribute contains attributes or coded attributes grouped under the same name (tag).

The introduced sample type attribute is used in the BIGPICTURE metadata model to differentiate between *Biological being*, *Specimen*, *Sample*, and *Slide* objects. The allowed values for sample types can be revised to allow for further differentiation if needed.

The possibility to link to other BIGPICTURE sample objects allows relations between samples to be encoded. This link is to be used to define a 'sampled from'-relation, i.e. to define how a *Slide* is prepared from one or several *Samples*, how a *Sample* is prepared from a *Specimen*, and how a *Specimen* is taken from a *Biological being*.

The name-value attribute list inherited from the EGA sample type can be used to encode simple metadata fields, such as for example *Sex* and *Age at extraction*. For metadata fields where value is a defined term in a controlled vocabulary (e.g. ontology or schema) the BIGPICTURE coded attribute type is to be used. This type allows an attribute to define attribute name, a coded value, and a schema that defines the code. Additionally, a clear text representation of the coded value is given as well as the possibility to define the version of the used schema. Such coded attributes are to be used to encode for example *Animal species*, *Anatomical site*, and *Fixation type*.

Some sample attributes are more complex and cannot be described using a single name-value or name-coded value attribute. For example, representing an immunohistochemistry stain is likely to require several attributes, such as protein target, antibody clone, reporter molecule, and fluorophore used. As a sample might have several such attributes, e.g. several stains, the entities for the attribute must be grouped together to separate them from entities of other attributes. Therefore, the BIGPICTURE sample type includes an attribute set type, that is defined by a name (e.g. *Staining*) and lists of simple or coded attributes. If needed, this type could further be extended to allow for further grouping by allowing the type to also have a list of the same type.

As with EGA sample objects, BIGPICTURE samples will further be defined and validated using checklists. These checklists can for example be specific for a given context (e.g. preclinical datasets) defined at the submission.

Image module

To represent a WSI image, a metadata object type is needed that can contain relevant technical metadata regarding the image, a list of files that contain the image data, as well as links to samples relevant to the image. Not unexpected, the EGA metadata model does not offer an object type suitable for representing image data. However, the EGA Analysis type is conceptually similar to the required type, as they both contain technical (genomic) metadata, a list of data files, and links to samples. The BIGPICTURE image type (**Figure 7**) is thus derived, but not extended from these types.

Figure 7. The BIGPICTURE Image type derives from the common EGA Object type. Similar to the EGA Run and Analysis type, the Image type references (links to) a study it is part of and files it contains. The sample or samples that is imaged is referenced in Sample refs. The Image can have simple attributes, coded attributes, and attribute sets.

To enable different types of images, i.e. not only WSI images but also e.g. gross images of specimens, the BIGPICTURE image type contains an *image type* attribute. An image is expected to link to at least one sample. For WSI images, this should be the slide sample that was imaged. As BIGPICTURE sample (except for *Biological beings*) objects will be required to further contain sample references, this allows the full hierarchy of pathological samples related to the image to be found (See **Figure 8**). A grossing image might instead reference to a specimen sample.

Figure 8. An image, for example a WSI, can link to the slide it images. The slide can further link to sample(s) it contain(s), these samples link to the specimen they were prepared from, and finally specimens link to the biological being they were extracted from.

The image data is contained in files separate from the image object, and these files are referenced to in similar fashion as in EGA Experiment and Run. Although DICOM is specified as the WSI image format, the image type is not dependent on the format used.

Simple technical metadata can be represented as simple name-value attributes, and more complex and/or advanced metadata by the coded attribute or attribute set types as described for the Sample module.

Annotation module

The Annotation object type (**Figure 9**) is to be used to present findings made on Image objects. The finding can either be in the form of graphical annotations (geometrical objects or segmentation maps) of an image, simple (coded) properties defining for example shapes or features found in an image, or a combination of these. The type of annotation is given in an *annotation type* attribute. An Annotation object is required to reference to the Image object on which the findings were made. The data for graphical annotation (i.e. coordinates and parameters defining geometrical shapes or images defining segmentation maps) are not part of the object, but instead included by referencing to a list of annotation data files. Similar to how the Image module does not require or assume DICOM to be used for images, there is no built-in limitation for the format of annotation data. Annotations can contain name-value, name-coded value, and name-attribute set attributes.

Figure 9. The BP Annotation type is similar to the BP Image type but references to images instead of to samples.

Observation module

An Observation object is considered to be a pathological statement about another CMMS entity or a set of CMMS entities at a given time point by one or more authors. The Observation object type can for example be used to state a diagnosis for a sample/image or set of samples/images (**Figure 10**). An Observation is required to reference at least one Sample object (*Biological being, Specimen, Sample, and/or Slide*) or Image for which the observation is true. The observation can be supported by additional references to Annotation objects, to provide evidence of the statement in terms of spatial and geometric descriptors. Further, an Observation can complement another Observation by reference. Observation metadata can be defined as name-value, name-coded value, and/or name-attribute set attributes. A diagnosis found in a referenced Sample can thus be given as a coded attribute, allowing different ontologies to be used, and the optical findings supporting the diagnosis given in referenced Annotation. Additionally, it is also possible to submit observation files (e.g. free-text reports or structured reports) and which are referenced by an observation object. However, it is not mandatory to provide an observation file for any given observation.

Figure 10. The BP Observation type is more complex than the BP Image and BP Annotation types. It allows references to samples, images, annotations, and other observations.

Study, Dataset, Policy, and DAC module

The Study module in the BIGPICTURE metadata model is similar in concept to the module in the EGA model, with the only additions being the added attribute types for coded attributes and attribute sets. Image, Annotation, and Observation objects are always part of, and thus must reference, a Study.

Also the Dataset module is similar to the EGA module, with the addition of references to Image, Annotation, and Observation objects (**Figure 11**). The Policy and DAC modules are the same as in the EGA model.

Figure 11. The BP Dataset type extends the EGA Dataset type to enable linking in the added image, annotation, and observation types.

Metrics Module

In order to facilitate decision making in terms of resource allocations to prioritize data collection based on current repository composition and for demonstrating progress towards data collection goals, the Collector Node Coordinator Board needs access to certain types of information about a dataset (e.g. country of origin, submitting laboratories). This class of metadata is coined Metrics Metadata from therein.

However, Metric Metadata might contain data considered to be non-disclosable to third parties by certain uploading parties. This results in a potential conflict of interest when a third party has been granted access to a certain dataset and would now be able to view this data.

Hence, it was decided to split Metrics Metadata from the dataset metadata and create a dedicated CMMS Entity termed Metrics (i.e. Metrics Module in context of the XML format) encapsulating it. Thereby, it will be possible in future that when a third party has gotten access to a dataset and related data (i.e. BP Samples, Observations, Images, Annotations) Metrics Metadata will not be shared with the third party.

As this concept is currently not captured by the EGA Model an appropriate format has to be developed. During the upcoming months the Task Force Metadata/Nomenclature will establish a definition of the Metrics CMMS Entity as well as an implementation of its Metrics Module format.

DICOM WSI format

WSIs typically contain image data from roughly a square cm area at up to 0.25 um/pixel resolution, resulting in gigapixel sized images. To enable efficient reading of the image, DICOM WSI format uses, like most WSI file formats, a tile arrangement to divide the image into smaller (e.g. 512 x 512 pixels) tiles. The DICOM WSI format requires that the tiles are arranged in a uniform and non-overlapping grid but does not specify any restrictions regarding tile size other than that the same size should be used within an instance (file).

To enable rapid viewing of the image at different zoom levels, the DICOM WSI format allows (like most WSI file formats) down sampled versions of the image data to be stored, forming a pyramid arrangement of down sampled images. The DICOM WSI format does not specify any requirements for how the pyramid levels should be related (e.g. the scaling factor used for down scaling or number of levels) other than that the levels should have a common frame of reference. Unlike most other WSI formats, each pyramid level, and also additional images such as macro or label images, is stored in a separate instance (file). Levels are associated into a WSI pyramid structure by having common identifiers in their metadata, namely the Series instance UID and Frame of reference UID.

Additionally, to image data, DICOM WSI can also store metadata for patient, the case the imaged slide belongs to, the pathology workflow that produced the imaged slide, the equipment and scan settings that was used to produce the slide, etc.

BIGPICTURE profile for DICOM WSI

To fulfil the set requirements for the unified open digital slide format, a stricter set of requirements than those given by the DICOM WSI specification is required. We call this subset of specifications the BIGPICTURE profile for DICOM WSI. The BIGPICTURE profile for the DICOM WSI format should stay compatible with DICOM WSI, e.g. a DICOM WSI from the BIGPICTURE repository should be fully viewable using standard DICOM WSI viewers. To further reduce the scope of options, we define subtypes of the BIGPICTURE DICOM WSI profile suitable for different use cases, such as brightfield imaging and fluorescence imaging. The identified requirements that the BIGPICTURE profile (and the subtypes) should address are listed below and further detailed in Appendix 1.

Fast random read access to tiles

To build a streaming service utilizing the DICOM WSI format, the initialization time for loading a DICOM WSI from disk, the access time for reading individual tiles from the WSI, and the time for rendering an image from the tiles must be within acceptable limits. Technically, this requirement can be fulfilled if the format:

- Allows fast access to essential technical metadata (such as image size, pixel type) without the need of loading (for the task) unnecessary other metadata.
- Provides indexes of byte positions and lengths for the frames in the file, and a fast way to determine the frame position from tile position.
- Only allows computationally efficient image compression formats.

Dimension Organization Type

DICOM WSI allows for two types of tile organization, called *tiled sparse* and *tiled full*. In sparse tile organization only tiles in identified ROI is included in the file, resulting in a smaller file size. Non-included tiles are typically rendered in a background colour. The tile position (x, y, z) and optical path of each included tile is stored in a list (*Per Frame Functional Groups Sequence*) that must be parsed to determine which tiles are available and the order (position) of these tiles in the file. In contrast, full tile organization results in marginally larger file size but a simpler frame arrangement. The increase in file size can be approximated by Equation 1. For example, if blank tiles are 1/10 of the size of a normal tile, and 50% of the tiles are sparse, the increase in size is 5%.

$$\text{size increase} = \frac{\text{blank tile size}}{\text{normal tile size}} * \text{sparseness}$$

Equation 1. Size increase for full tiled vs sparse tiled organization. Blank and normal tile size are the typical sizes (in bytes) of the

added tiles and existing tiles, respectively, when converting a sparsely tiled image to fully tiled. Sparseness is the fraction of tiles that are sparse.

For full tile organization DICOM WSI specifies that tiles should be ordered by column, row, focal plane, and optical path. Additionally, number of tile columns and rows, focal planes and optical paths are required to be defined. It is thus possible to directly determine the frame order of a tile simply from tile position (x, y, z) and optical path. The loading times for otherwise equivalent DICOM WSIs with sparse or full tile organization is presented in **Table 2**. To reduce parsing time during loading and thus provide fast tile access, the dimension organization type should be *tiled full*.

Table 2. Loading times for DICOM WSI file sets in sparsely or fully tiled configuration and with and without BOT.

	WITHOUT BOT	WITH BOT
SPARSELY TILED	3.846 s	4.062 s
FULLY TILED	0.205 s	0.030 s

Frame index

The image data in a DICOM file can store multiple frames, as in the case for WSI files. The frame data for each frame is preceded by an *item tag* followed by the frame length. To enable random tile access, the start of each frame must be known in order for the reader to directly go to the frame of the requested tile. DICOM WSI presents four options for indexing the byte positions of frames in the file:

- No index. To determine the frame byte positions the image data needs to be parsed by reading each *item tag* and frame length. As the image data can be large (in the order of gigabytes for the base level) this procedure is slow.
- Using a basic offset table (BOT). A BOT contains the frame byte positions for each frame/tile represented by a 32-bit unsigned integer per frame. The size of the BOT is significantly smaller than the image data, thus providing faster indexing of the frames compared to having no index. As the offsets are represented by 32-bit integers, the maximum image data size a BOT can index is approximately 4 GB. If concatenation is used (image data is split into multiple files) each file has a separate BOT, thus allowing the total size to exceed 4 GB.
- Using an extended offset table (EOT). An EOT is similar to a BOT but with 64-bit unsigned integers thus allowing indexing of files larger than 4 GB.
- TIFF-DICOM duality. TIFF-files allow frame byte offsets and lengths to be stored in specific tags. As DICOM allows TIFF metadata to be embedded (in the DICOM), such tags can be used to index the frames. An added benefit of this solution is that many proprietary WSI formats are based on TIFF and support for TIFF is widespread in WSI software. Enforcing such dual personality files could make it easier for existing software to read DICOM files. However, neither a pure TIFF- or DICOM implementation would be able to read the complete information available in the file out of the box.

To decrease complexity and provide full DICOM compatibility, dual personality TIFF-DICOM should not be used. The loading time for otherwise equivalent DICOM WSI files with and without BOT present is presented in **Table 2**. As an EOT is double the size of a BOT (64-bit vs. 32-bit values), the parsing time should be higher. In BIGPICTURE DICOM WSI, frames should be indexed using a BOT if possible, and using an EOT if needed due to the image data size.

Compression formats

The DICOM standard supports a range of image compression formats (transfer syntaxes), including the (for WSI application most relevant) 8-bit JPEG and lossy JPEG 2000. Restricting the options to only JPEG could improve viewing performance (as it is less compute-expensive, see 4) and compatibility (as for example JPEG2000 is less supported in web browser). On the other hand, JPEG2000 is more suitable for high dynamic range images (such as fluorescence images) due to the support of up to 32 bits per component and produces less compression artifacts. In general, transcoding from one format to another is computationally expensive (**Table 3**) and introduces generation loss and should thus be avoided. For BIGPICTURE WSI DICOM image data should preferably be compressed in 8-bit JPEG, with the option to use JPEG 2000 if need to preserve the imaged data (e.g. to avoid reducing bit depth or to avoid data re-compression). Future image

formats suitable for digital pathology, such as JPEG-XL, should be allowed once implemented into the DICOM standard. Uncompressed, RLE lossless, JPEG lossless, or JPEG-LS formats should not be used.

Table 3. Conversion time for lossy vs lossless conversion methods. Lossy conversion involves uncompressing and re-compression of the image data and is thus more computational intensive. The conversion time can therefore be reduced by multithreading, as the computational resources are increased. Lossless conversion is less limited by computational resources and more limited by data transfer speed (i.e. read and write performance). Thus, the conversion benefits less by multithreading.

	SVS FILE	NPDI FILE
LOSSY SINGLE THREAD	86.5 s	68.5 s
LOSSY MULTI THREAD	32.5 s	24.0 s
LOSSLESS SINGLE THREAD	7.94 s	36.0 s
LOSSLESS MULTI THREAD	8.59 s	20.3 s

Table 4. Decoding comparison for JPEG and JPEG2000. Decoding JPEG2000 (using an openly available decoder) is significantly slower than decoding JPEG.

COMPRESSION FORMAT	DECODE TIME
JPEG	0.5 ms
JPEG 2000	4.8 ms

Metadata in DICOM tags

The DICOM standard is designed to not only contain image data but also related metadata regarding, for example, patient, specimen preparation, and imaging conditions, thus offering to cover more CMMS entities than just Image. Providing more than minimum required metadata in DICOM makes the metadata parsable for generic DICOM readers. However, making updates to submitted datasets will be expensive and complicated if the updated metadata is also to be reflected into the DICOM files. The BIGPICTURE DICOM WSI profile should therefore only contain minimal required metadata. Solutions for adding corresponding metadata to the DICOM files upon for example download will be considered.

Tile size used for image data.

Typical tile size for WSIs is between 240 to 1024 pixels wide and high. Some WSI formats defines or allows tile overlap or irregular tile positions and sizes. The DICOM WSI standard allows for any tile size to be used, also within a pyramid, but the tiles must be arranged in a regular grid and must not overlap. Enforcing the same tile size for all levels in a WSI simplifies the ‘deep zooming’ viewing frameworks used for fast viewing of large image data. The BIGPICTURE profile therefore specifies uniform tile size for all pyramid levels, and regular and non-overlapping tile arrangement. Enforcing the same tile size for all WSIs could be beneficial for AI performance. However, restricting to only one tile size could also limit the usability of the BIGPICTURE repository and would require extensive retiling of image data to be submitted.

Number of pyramid levels and scaling factor between levels.

The DICOM standard does not specify that a certain number of lower resolution levels to be available, or the scaling factor between levels. For viewing performance, it is beneficial if the pyramid contains every dyadic level (that is, scaled by 2) from the base layer and up and that the imaged area at the highest (lowest resolution) level is less than one tile in size. For the BIGPICTURE DICOM WSI profile the pyramid should

have an integer scale between levels, the integer scale should be a power to 2, and there should be a pyramid level for each power of 2 until the scaled level is less than one tile in size.

Optical path identifiers

DICOM identifies optical paths in files with a unique identifier for the instance/file, but does not require that the same identifier is used for the same optical path across all instances/files in a pyramid. To make it easier to keep track of optical paths, optical paths should have the same identifier across all files of the WSI.

Allowed image types

A DICOM WSI can contain four types of images: *volume*, *label*, *overview*, and *thumbnail*. *Volume* is used for pyramid levels, *label* for imaging the label of the slide, *overview* for macro images of the whole slide (possibly including the label), and *thumbnail* for a “low” resolution non-tiled image of the pyramid. *Volume* type is essential for representing the WSI and is thus an allowed image type. As slide labels are likely to contain personal information, allowing them to be used in BIGPICTURE makes anonymisation and anonymisation verification more difficult. Label image types is thus not allowed in BIGPICTURE WSI DICOM. If the information on the label is important to be included, it should be encoded elsewhere (for example as text in the Label Text attribute). Overview (macro) images are important for quality control and such be included in the WSI if available. If the overview contains the slide label, the label should be cropped out. The use of *thumbnail* is optional. The current DICOM WSI specification mandates that imaged volume (i.e. image physical size and focal depth) as well as pixel spacing is defined for Overview (and Label) image types. A relaxation of these requirements is expected to be included in the DICOM standard early 2022, and the BIGPICTURE WSI format does therefore not require these attributes for Overview image type.

BIGPICTURE WSI subtypes

Although the BIGPICTURE WSI profile narrows the options available in the DICOM WSI format, there is still variations and conditional requirement present. To further reduce these variations, subtypes of the profile are specified. Additional subtypes can be defined if needed, for example for TMAs.

Brightfield subtype

The brightfield subtype specifies a photometric interpretation corresponding to either RGB or YCbCr (luma and blue and red chroma components), 3 samples per pixel, that the illumination type is either brightfield or transmission, and a full spectrum illumination source. Only one optical path is allowed. An ICC profile is required.

Fluorescence subtype

The fluorescence subtype uses photometric interpretation MONOCHROME2, meaning a monochrome image where pixel value 0 is to be interpreted as no signal and 255 (if 8 bit depth) as full signal. Each fluorescence channel used is to be encoded as a separate optical path and multiple optical paths are therefore allowed. Illumination type should be Epifluorescence and illumination source either full spectrum or defined by optical wavelength (depending on source). Specification of optical excitation and emission filters and look-up tables are optional.

Concatenated files.

DICOM supports files (instances) to be split up into multiple files, for example by optical path, focal plane and/or frame index. This can be used to reduce individual file size (if needed). As of CP1818, extended offset tables are the preferred solution unless working on filesystem limiting the file size to 4GB such as FAT32. BIGPICTURE will not use concatenation since this is not a relevant scenario.

Graphical annotation format

Graphical annotations for WSIs are either defined by geometric shapes or by segmentation maps. As geometrical shapes are defined by 2D or 3D coordinates and/or parameters and segmentation maps (typically) by an image, the two types of annotations required different formats.

Geometric shapes

A format for annotations defined by geometric shapes needs to be able to define commonly used geometries such as point, polyline, polygon, polygon with holes, rectangle, and circles. Annotations can be produced with coordinates (and parameters) in physical units (e.g. mm) or pixels. For physical units, the format must standardize or specify the physical unit used as well as the coordinate origin versus the origin of the image the annotation is made on. Annotations with pixel units need to be mapped to a suitable pixel sized version of the image, e.g. a pyramid level within the WSI, and can use the same origin as the image. The mapping can be done either by specifically referring to a pyramid level or by more generally specifying the pixel size the annotation is using. In the proposed metadata schema annotation objects link to WSIs as a whole and not to specific pyramid levels. Thus, annotation defined in pixel units needs to define the pixel spacing.

The BIGPICTURE WSI frontend Cytomine will likely be used both for reading annotations submitted into the repository and to make new annotations to be submitted into the repository. Cytomine currently supports geometrical annotations, in the shape of points, lines, polygons, etc defined by pixel coordinates. The annotation can have multiple types of metadata, for example be associated with (multiple) terms (properties defined by an ontology), tag-value properties, tags, and also files. A BIGPICTURE WSI annotation format for geometric shapes should allow annotations to be serialized in either direction to Cytomine's annotation format.

DICOM specifies two types of annotation formats for annotations defined by geometric shapes: structured reports and microscope bulk simple annotations. A structured report can define measurements as well as observations and findings and use geometric shapes as *evidence* for the statements. The geometric shape can either be defined as 2D or 3D coordinates. When using 2D coordinates, the coordinates are in pixel units and are then related to a specific image instance (e.g. a pyramid level in a WSI) and the allowed geometry types are *point*, *multipoint*, *polyline*, *circle*, and *ellipse*. 3D coordinates are defined in physical units (mm) with a specified frame of reference as origin (matching the frame of reference of the DICOM WSI), with allowed geometry types *point*, *multipoint*, *polyline*, *polygon*, *ellipse*, and *ellipsoid*. Structured reports offer high flexibility for representing different annotations and metadata for the annotations, but this comes at the cost of simplicity. Structured reports can therefore be computationally heavy to both create and to parse and are therefore likely not suitable for representing large numbers of annotations. Structured report annotations were created by converting the annotations made on the AIDA DRSK dataset using Highdicom, and a representative and shortened version is presented in appendix 2. An important limitation of the *polygon* geometry type DICOM structured reports uses is that there is no mechanism for explicitly encoding holes in the polygon. Such geometry must thus be defined using a *keyhole* technique, where the hole is defined by adding additional points to form a 0-width channel between the inner and outer contour. Annotations defined with the *keyhole* technique are however not fully serializable to formats with full polygon with hole-support, as additional coordinates must be added. Cytomine annotations, that allow polygons with holes, can thus not be fully serialized to DICOM structured reports.

DICOM microscope bulk simple annotations were introduced into DICOM in 2021 by the supplement 222 with the intention to provide a simpler and more efficient format for annotations, specifically designed for AI generated annotations of WSIs. The flexibility to encode a wide variety of findings etc. is reduced. Microscope bulk simple annotations can be grouped in annotation groups containing similar annotation properties and geometrical type. All coordinates for the annotations in the group are then given in the same array of floats and an index is used to locate the start and end of each annotation in the array. The group can have properties defining what is annotated (e.g. tissue or anatomical structure, cells or nucleus), anatomical region the annotated parts originate from, measurements, and how it was created (manually, semiautomatic or fully automatic, etc). As with geometric shapes defined in DICOM structured reports, shapes are defined either in 2D or 3D coordinates, where 2D coordinates are always in pixel size and 3D coordinates are in physical size. The allowed geometry types are for both coordinate definitions *point*, *polyline*, *polygon*, *ellipse*, and *rectangle*. Microscope bulk annotations were created by converting the annotations made on the AIDA DRSK dataset using Wsidicom, and a representative and shortened version is presented in appendix 3. As with geometries defined in structured reports, polygons with holes are not allowed, and further the *keyhole* technique is forbidden. It is thus not possible to encode polygons containing holes. Additionally, DICOM microscope bulk simple annotations offer only a limited set of and limited number of metadata attributes. It is thus not possible to fully serialize from Cytomine's annotation format to DICOM microscope bulk simple annotations.

Two more generic formats for representing geometrical shapes that are commonly used for WSI annotations are GeoJSON and Well-known text (WKT). Both these formats support (among other) *point*, *linestring* and *polygon* geometries as well as multipart and collections of such geometries and it is possible to convert between the two formats. Polygons in these formats can contain holes without limitations. Although these

formats are used in popular open source WSI software, such as QuPath and Cytomine, there are no well-established and widely used standards for using these for WSI annotations. Such a standard should, for example, define how pixel and physical unit coordinates are mapped to a WSI in terms of pixel spacing, common origin and orientation etc, and how to encode ontology data. As serialization to Cytomine's annotation format is important, we proposed that the main annotation format to be used in BIGPICTURE is based on the same, or compatible, format for representing geometrical shapes (e.g. GeoJSON or WKT), and allows for the same types of metadata as defined in Cytomine's format (e.g. tags, terms, key-value properties). How the annotation format should define the image annotated, coordinate type, and coordinate origin is to be further discussed.

Segmentation maps

Segmentation maps are essentially images that classify the source WSI either with binary (true or false), integer (e.g. 0-255) or float (e.g. 0.0-1.0) information. The map can either be directly linked to image in the WSI pyramid or, more generally, to a pixel spacing. Segmentation maps of high resolution present the same challenges as WSIs, in that the image is too large to fit into memory and random access to part of the image becomes inefficient. Such maps therefore need the same tiling and pyramid approach as WSIs to be usable. The DICOM Segmentation IOD is one format for segmentation maps that enables the map to be tiled and also to define the map in a series of pixel spacings. As the methods for creating and using such segmentation maps is similar to the methods for WSI images, DICOM is likely a suitable format for representing segmentation maps in the BIGPICTURE repository.

Suggested supported annotation formats

As it is possible that other tools will create annotations in the DICOM annotation formats for submission to BIGPICTURE, we proposed that it should be possible to submit and use those formats in the repository. The main annotation format for annotations of geometric shapes should however be more compatible with the Cytomine annotation format. The main hurdle for defining such format is how to establish and keep the link to the image that is annotated. For segmentation maps we propose that the DICOM segmentation format should be used, as it allows the same frameworks as used for DICOM WSI to be re-used to a large extent.

Format specification revisions

This document describes a proposal of an initial version of the BIGPICTURE submission format. During the design of the format, we have identified a need for a living standard that is updated as the technology develops. We therefore propose to hand over the responsibility to adopt this submission format as a standard for the infrastructure to the Taskforce Metadata/Nomenclature. We further propose that the taskforce becomes responsible for coordinating the work of developing the submission format throughout the length of the project as well adopting new versions as a standard.

The BIGPICTURE submission format describes a way to encode imaging, annotation and other metadata. A number of metadata field will be required at submission as defined by the MSMdad document. However, additional optional data can be submitted, and it will even be allowed to submit data that go outside the format. We therefore also see a need to maintain public documentation of what type of support can be expected from the infrastructure after submission. This documentation should be published together with an easy-to-use documentation of the format at the data submission portal once the first version of the portal has been launched.

We further propose that the standard will make use of three types of simple statuses, that is a simplified version of the W3C standards process, that emphasizes the need for implementation experience before approval⁹.

- **Draft:** any standard descriptions that are being worked on. These can be suggested by anyone, but the Taskforce Metadata/Nomenclature should be notified. This status marks anything that has not been approved yet by the Task Force.
- **Candidate:** standard descriptions in the form of a report adopted by the Task Force
- **Approved:** standard descriptions where the Task Force has verified that:

- Test data exists
- A reference implementation exists
- The support in the infrastructure has been documented
- Feedback from the reference implementation has been worked into the standard

At the moment we propose to the Task Force Metadata/Nomenclature that the following parts of the submission format should get the following statuses:

NAME	DESCRIPTION	STATUS
METADATA FORMAT	The part of this document under the metadata format heading, excluding Metrics.	Candidate
IMAGING FORMAT	The part of this document under DICOM WSI Format	Candidate
GRAPHICAL ANNOTATION FORMAT	The part of this document under Graphical annotation format.	Draft

The reason for not proposing that the Graphical annotation format should be adopted as a Candidate standard is that not enough testing has been performed to understand how the workflow of creating annotations in Cytomine and the EGA infrastructure should work. In addition, a need doesn't yet exist to define this for any of the upcoming deliveries. We estimate that a need for a graphical annotation format will arise once the project goes past M18.

In addition to marking the first format description reaching draft status we propose that the metadata taskforce should submit a standard of practice description (SOP) to the BIGPICTURE managing board describing how the submission format is maintained.

Conclusion

In this report we have described the background and work to create a unified open digital slide and annotation format, that we hand over to the Task Force Metadata/Nomenclature for adoption as a standard within the BIGPICTURE platform. The report describes work and recommendations about digital slide format in DICOM, metadata encoding using XML schemas and various annotation formats.

To create a unified open digital slide and annotation format, we have made a number of interpretations of the description of the deliverable where we have focused on the purpose of the format.

The BIGPICTURE platform is based on existing technology that specifies a submission as metadata in a specific *schema* that is combined with data files in terms of images. The *schema* is instantiated as XML files with filename references to the data files. Data submitters package their data in a submission format and submit through a data submission portal. Once data has been submitted, the data is stored as is and is used by a number of services and it is possible to download the submitted data. In this work, we therefore defined the unified format as the format used for submission, we then leave it up the creators of the infrastructure to decide what to do with the data. We assume however, it is likely that the submitted data will remain as is.

When submitting data using this existing technology, a submission consists of metadata, digital slides, observations and annotations as complete package. Some metadata make sense to organize next to an annotation such as labels for machine learning and some metadata make sense to store next to imaging data such as technical information about the digital slide scanner. Therefore, we see metadata, digital slides, observation and annotation as an interlinked whole.

That being said, we can still leave it open to WP3 and the Task Force Metadata/Nomenclature to decide what fields are required in different settings. But we need to ensure that all metadata can be encoded by the format. However, there is also a technical need to make certain metadata mandatory since it is needed to correctly display the imaging data, such as pixel spacing or an ICC profile.

Appendix 1. BIGPICTURE DICOM WSI profile

Base type

MODULE	TAG	NAME	TYPE	BP TYPE	VALUE/COMMENT	CMMS FIELD
SOP COMMON	0008,0016	SOP Class UID	1	1	1.2.840.10008.5.1.4.1.1.77.1.6	FIELD ID 123: DICOM Image Type
SOP COMMON	0008,0018	Sop Instance UID	1	1	BP-generated UID	
PATIENT	0010,0010	Patient's Name	2	E	Empty	
PATIENT	0010,0020	Patient ID	2	E	Empty	
PATIENT	0010,0030	Patients' Birth Date	2	E	Empty	
PATIENT	0010,0040	Patient's Sex	2	E	Empty	
GENERAL STUDY	0008,0020	Study Date	2	E	Empty	
GENERAL STUDY	0008,0030	Study Time	2	E	Empty	
GENERAL STUDY	0008,0050	Accession Number	2	E	Empty	
GENERAL STUDY	0020,000D	Study Instance UID	1	1	BP-generated UID	
GENERAL STUDY	0020,0010	Study ID	2	E	Empty	
GENERAL SERIES	0008,0060	Modality	1	1	SM	
GENERAL SERIES	0020,000E	Series Instance UID	1	1	BP-generated UID	
GENERAL SERIES	0020,0011	Series Number	2	E	Empty	
FRAME OF REFERENCE	0020,0052	Frame of Reference UID	1	1	BP-generated UID	
ENHANCED GENERAL EQUIPMENT	0008,0070	Manufacturer	1	1	Scanner Manufactor's Name	FIELD 61: Scanner Manufactor's Name
ENHANCED GENERAL EQUIPMENT	0008,1090	Manufacturer's Model Name	1	1	Scanner Name	FIELD 58: Manufacturer's Model Name

945358-BIGPICTURE-- D4.03

ENHANCED GENERAL EQUIPMENT	0018,1000	Device Serial Number	1	1	Unknown (Anonymized)	FIELD 166: Device Serial Number
ENHANCED GENERAL EQUIPMENT	0018,1020	Software Versions	1	1	Software Versions	FIELD ID 60: Software Versions
IMAGE PIXEL	0028,0006	Planar Configuration	1C	1	0	
IMAGE PIXEL	0028,0010	Rows	1	1	Tile size width	FIELD ID 175: Base Layer Tile size
IMAGE PIXEL	0028,0011	Columns	1	1	Tile size height	FIELD ID 175: Base Layer Tile size
IMAGE PIXEL	0028,0100	Bits Allocated	1	1		
IMAGE PIXEL	0028,0101	Bits Stored	1	1	Color depth	FIELD ID 67: Color Depth
IMAGE PIXEL	0028,0102	High Bit	1	1		
IMAGE PIXEL	0028,0103	Pixel Representation	1	1	0	
MULTI-FRAME FUNCTIONAL GROUPS	0008,0023	Content Date	1	1	Date DICOM file was created	
MULTI-FRAME FUNCTIONAL GROUPS	0008,0033	Content Time	1	1	Time DICOM file was created	
MULTI-FRAME FUNCTIONAL GROUPS	0020,0013	Instance Number	1	1		
MULTI-FRAME FUNCTIONAL GROUPS	0028,0008	Number of Frames	1	1		
MULTI-FRAME FUNCTIONAL GROUPS	5200,9229	Shared Functional Groups Sequence	1	1		
MULTI-FRAME FUNCTIONAL GROUPS	5200,9230	Per-frame Functional Groups Sequence	1	N	Not present	

945358-BIGPICTURE- D4.03

MULTI-FRAME DIMENSION	0020,9221	Dimension Organization Sequence	1	1		
MULTI-FRAME DIMENSION	0020,9311	Dimension Organization Type	3	1	TILED_FULL	
SPECIMEN	0040,0512	Container Identifier	1	1	Unknown (Anonymized)	FIELD ID 55: Slide-ID
SPECIMEN	0040,0513	Issuer of the Container Identifier Sequence	2	E	Empty	
SPECIMEN	0040,0518	Container Type Code Sequence	2	E	Empty	
SPECIMEN	0040,0560	Specimen Description Sequence	1	1		
>SPECIMEN DESCRIPTION SEQUENCE	0040,0551	Specimen Identifier	1	1	Unknown (Anonymized)	FIELD ID 48: Sample-ID
>SPECIMEN DESCRIPTION SEQUENCE	0040,0554	Specimen UID	1	1	BP-generated UID	FIELD ID 43 : Specimen-ID
WHOLE SLIDE MICROSCOPY IMAGE	0008,0008	Image Type	1	1	ORIGINAL/DERIVED, PRIMARY, VOLUME/OVERVIEW/THUMBNAIL, NONE/RESAMPLED	
WHOLE SLIDE MICROSCOPY IMAGE	0008,002A	Acquisition DateTime	1	1	Anonymized	
WHOLE SLIDE MICROSCOPY IMAGE	0008,9206	Volumetric Properties	1	1	VOLUME	
WHOLE SLIDE MICROSCOPY IMAGE	0028,0301	Burned in Annotation	1	1	No	FIELD ID 176: Biological Being Identifier Present in Image

945358-BIGPICTURE- D4.03

WHOLE SLIDE MICROSCOPY IMAGE	0028,2110	Lossy Image Compression	1	1	00 (Never lossy compressed) or 01 (compressed lossy)	FIELD ID 183: Compression Status
WHOLE SLIDE MICROSCOPY IMAGE	0028,2112	Lossy Image Compression Ratio	1C	1C	Approximate value of x:1. Required if Lossy Image Compression is 01	FIELD ID 68: Lossy Image Compression Ratio
WHOLE SLIDE MICROSCOPY IMAGE	0028,2114	Lossy Image Compression Method	1C	1C	Multiple values if re-compressed. Required if Lossy Image Compression is 01	FIELD ID 69: Lossy Image Compression Method
WHOLE SLIDE MICROSCOPY IMAGE	0048,0001	Imaged Volume Width	1	1C	Required if image type is VOLUME	can be computed as FIELD ID 64: Image Shape x Pixel Resolution
WHOLE SLIDE MICROSCOPY IMAGE	0048,0002	Imaged Volume Height	1	1C	Required if image type is VOLUME	can be computed as FIELD ID 64: Image Shape x Pixel Resolution
WHOLE SLIDE MICROSCOPY IMAGE	0048,0003	Imaged Volume Depth	1	1C	Required if image type is VOLUME	Can be computed
WHOLE SLIDE MICROSCOPY IMAGE	0048,0006	Total Pixel Matrix COLUMNS	1	1	Image size in pixels	FIELD ID 64: Image Shape
WHOLE SLIDE MICROSCOPY IMAGE	0048,0007	Total Pixel Matrix Rows	1	1	Image size in pixels	FIELD ID 64: Image Shape
WHOLE SLIDE MICROSCOPY IMAGE	0048,0008	Total Pixel Matrix Origin Sequence	1	1	Position of image data vs slide	FIELD ID 168: Total Pixel Matrix Origin Sequence
WHOLE SLIDE MICROSCOPY IMAGE	0048,0010	Specimen Label in Image	1	1	No	FIELD ID 174: Has Label
WHOLE SLIDE MICROSCOPY IMAGE	0048,0011	Focus Method	1	1	AUTO or MANUAL	FIELD ID 113: Focus Method

945358-BIGPICTURE-- D4.03

WHOLE SLIDE MICROSCOPY IMAGE	0048,0012	Extended Depth of Field	1	1	YES or NO	FIELD ID 114: Extended Depth of Field
WHOLE SLIDE MICROSCOPY IMAGE	0048,0013	Number of Focal Planes	1C	1C	Required if Extended Depth of Field is YES	FIELD ID 170: Number of Focal Planes
WHOLE SLIDE MICROSCOPY IMAGE	0048,0014	Distance Between Focal Planes	1C	1C	Required if Extended Depth of Field is YES	FIELD ID 171: Spacing between Focal Planes
WHOLE SLIDE MICROSCOPY IMAGE	0048,0102	Image Orientation (Slide)	1	1	Orientation of image data vs slide	FIELD ID 181: Image Orientation
WHOLE SLIDE MICROSCOPY IMAGE	0048,0303	Total Pixel matrix Focal Planes	1C	1	Number of focal planes	FIELD ID 64: Image Shape
>SHARED FUNCTIONAL GROUPS SEQUENCE	0028,9110	Pixel Measures Sequence	1	1C	Required if image type is VOLUME	
>PIXEL MEASURES SEQUENCE	0018,0050	Slice Thickness	1C	1C	Depth of field, Required if image type is VOLUME	FIELD ID 182: Depth of Field
>PIXEL MEASURES SEQUENCE	0018,0088	Spacing between Slices	1C	1C	Spacing between focal planes. Required if multiple focal planes	FIELD ID 171: Spacing between Focal Planes
>PIXEL MEASURES SEQUENCE	0028,0030	Pixel Spacing	1	1C	Required if image type is VOLUME	FIELD ID 65: Image Resolution
OPTICAL PATH	0048,0105	Optical Path Sequence	1	1	Multiple items if multiple paths	FIELD ID 177: Optical Path Set
>OPTICAL PATH SEQUENCE ITEM	0022,001A	Channel Description Code Sequence	1C	N	Not present	
>OPTICAL PATH SEQUENCE ITEM	0048,0106	Optical Path Identifier	1	1	Unique identifier	FIELD ID 177: Optical Path Set
>OPTICAL PATH SEQUENCE ITEM	0048,0107	Optical Path Description	3	1		

945358-BIGPICTURE– D4.03

>OPTICAL PATH SEQUENCE ITEM	0048,0112	Objective Lens Power	3	1	Magnification	FIELD ID 63: Magnification
SLIDE LABEL	2200,0002	Label Text	2	N	Not present	
SLIDE LABEL	2200,0005	Barcode Value	2	N	Not present	
IMAGE PIXEL	7FE0,0001	Extended Offset Table	3	1C	Required if image data is > 4GB	
IMAGE PIXEL	7FE0,0002	Extended Offset Table Lengths	3	1C	Required if image data is > 4GB	
IMAGE PIXEL	7FE0,0010	Pixel Data	1C	1	With non-empty BOT unless EOT is used	

Fluorescence imaging type

MODULE	TAG	NAME	TYPE	BP TYPE	VALUE/COMMENT	CMMS FIELD
IMAGE PIXEL	0028,0002	Samples per Pixel	1	1	1	FIELD ID 67: Color Depth
IMAGE PIXEL	0028,0004	Photometric Interpretation	1	1	MONOCHROME2	FIELD ID 66: Color Space
>OPTICAL PATH SEQUENCE ITEM	0048,0120	Palette Color Lookup Table Sequence	3	3	Optional LUT	
>OPTICAL PATH SEQUENCE ITEM	0022,0055	Illumination Wave Length	1C	1C	Required if Illumination Wave Length not present	FIELD ID 118: Illumination Wave Length Attribute (Conditionally) or Illumination Color Code Sequence Attribute (Conditionally)
>OPTICAL PATH SEQUENCE ITEM	0048,0108	Illumination Color Code Sequence	1C	1C	Required if Illumination Color Code Sequence not present	FIELD ID 118: Illumination Wave Length Attribute (Conditionally) or Illumination Color Code Sequence Attribute (Conditionally)
>OPTICAL PATH SEQUENCE ITEM	0022,0016	Illumination Type Code Sequence	1	1	Epifluorescence illumination	FIELD 117: Illumination Type Code Sequence Attribute
>OPTICAL PATH SEQUENCE ITEM	0022,0001	Light Path Filter Pass-Through Wavelength	3	3	Optional excitation filter	
>OPTICAL PATH SEQUENCE ITEM	0022,0002	Light Path Filter Pass Band	3	3	Optional excitation filter	

945358-BIGPICTURE– D4.03

>OPTICAL PATH SEQUENCE ITEM	0022,0003	Image Path Filter Pass-Through Wavelength	3	3	Optional emission filter	
>OPTICAL PATH SEQUENCE ITEM	0022,0004	Image Path Filter Pass Band	3	3	Optional emission filter	
OPTICAL PATH	0048,0302	Number of Optical Paths	1C	1	Number of optical paths in file	FIELD ID 177: Optical Path Set

Brightfield imaging type

MODULE	TAG	NAME	TYPE	BP TYPE	VALUE/COMMENT	CMMS FIELD
IMAGE PIXEL	0028,0002	Samples per Pixel	1	1	3	FIELD ID 66: Color Space
IMAGE PIXEL	0028,0004	Photometric Interpretation	1	1	YBR_FULL, YBR_FULL_422, YBR_ICT, YBR_RCT, RGB	FIELD ID 66: Color Space
>OPTICAL PATH SEQUENCE ITEM	0028,2000	ICC Profile	1C	1		FIELD ID 180: Color Profile
>OPTICAL PATH SEQUENCE ITEM	0022,0016	Illumination Type Code Sequence	1	1	Brightfield illumination or Transmission illumination	FIELD 117: Illumination Type Code Sequence Attribute
>OPTICAL PATH SEQUENCE ITEM	0048,0108	Illumination Color Code Sequence	1C	1	Full Spectrum	FIELD ID 118: Illumination Wave Length Attribute (Conditionally) or Illumination Color Code Sequence Attribute (Conditionally)
OPTICAL PATH	0048,0302	Number of Optical Paths	1C	1	1	FIELD ID 177: Optical Path Set

Appendix 2. Annotation in DICOM structured report format

(0008, 0016) SOP Class UID UI: Comprehensive SR Storage
 (0008, 0018) SOP Instance UID UI: 2.25.174602519212920404501769419536083500829
 (0008, 0020) Study Date DA: "
 (0008, 0023) Content Date DA: '20210923'
 (0008, 0030) Study Time TM: "
 (0008, 0033) Content Time TM: '095239.808757'
 (0008, 0050) Accession Number SH: "
 (0008, 0060) Modality CS: 'SR'
 (0008, 0070) Manufacturer LO: "
 (0008, 0090) Referring Physician's Name PN: "
 (0008, 1111) Referenced Performed Procedure Step Sequence 0 item(s) ----
 (0010, 0010) Patient's Name PN: "
 (0010, 0020) Patient ID LO: "
 (0010, 0030) Patient's Birth Date DA: "
 (0010, 0040) Patient's Sex CS: "
 (0020, 000d) Study Instance UID UI: 2.25.18232434223853928855678035920098554611
 (0020, 000e) Series Instance UID UI: 2.25.104726606032138908411845871032243314324
 (0020, 0010) Study ID SH: "
 (0020, 0011) Series Number IS: '1'
 (0020, 0013) Instance Number IS: '1'
 (0040, a040) Value Type CS: 'CONTAINER'
 (0040, a043) Concept Name Code Sequence 1 item(s) ----
 (0008, 0100) Code Value SH: '126000'
 (0008, 0102) Coding Scheme Designator SH: 'DCM'
 (0008, 0104) Code Meaning LO: 'Imaging Measurement Report'

 (0040, a050) Continuity Of Content CS: 'CONTINUOUS'
 (0040, a372) Performed Procedure Code Sequence 0 item(s) ----
 (0040, a375) Current Requested Procedure Evidence Sequence 1 item(s) ----
 (0008, 1115) Referenced Series Sequence 1 item(s) ----
 (0008, 1199) Referenced SOP Sequence 1 item(s) ----
 (0008, 1150) Referenced SOP Class UID UI: VL Whole Slide Microscopy Image Storage
 (0008, 1155) Referenced SOP Instance UID UI: 2.25.2852436523387486548764868821770429897

 (0020, 000e) Series Instance UID UI: 2.25.104726606032138908411845871032243314324

 (0020, 000d) Study Instance UID UI: 2.25.18232434223853928855678035920098554611

 (0040, a491) Completion Flag CS: 'PARTIAL'
 (0040, a493) Verification Flag CS: 'UNVERIFIED'
 (0040, a496) Preliminary Flag CS: 'PRELIMINARY'
 (0040, a504) Content Template Sequence 1 item(s) ----
 (0008, 0105) Mapping Resource CS: 'DCMR'
 (0040, db00) Template Identifier CS: '1500'

 (0040, a730) Content Sequence 4 item(s) ----
 (0040, a010) Relationship Type CS: 'HAS CONCEPT MOD'
 (0040, a040) Value Type CS: 'CODE'

(0040, a043) Concept Name Code Sequence 1 item(s) ----
 (0008, 0100) Code Value SH: '121049'
 (0008, 0102) Coding Scheme Designator SH: 'DCM'
 (0008, 0104) Code Meaning LO: 'Language of Content Item and Descendants'

 (0040, a168) Concept Code Sequence 1 item(s) ----
 (0008, 0100) Code Value SH: 'en-US'
 (0008, 0102) Coding Scheme Designator SH: 'RFC5646'
 (0008, 0104) Code Meaning LO: 'English (United States)'

 (0040, a010) Relationship Type CS: 'HAS CONCEPT MOD'
 (0040, a040) Value Type CS: 'CODE'
 (0040, a043) Concept Name Code Sequence 1 item(s) ----
 (0008, 0100) Code Value SH: '121058'
 (0008, 0102) Coding Scheme Designator SH: 'DCM'
 (0008, 0104) Code Meaning LO: 'Procedure reported'

 (0040, a168) Concept Code Sequence 1 item(s) ----
 (0008, 0100) Code Value SH: '363679005'
 (0008, 0102) Coding Scheme Designator SH: 'SCT'
 (0008, 0104) Code Meaning LO: 'Imaging procedure'

 (0040, a010) Relationship Type CS: 'CONTAINS'
 (0040, a040) Value Type CS: 'CONTAINER'
 (0040, a043) Concept Name Code Sequence 1 item(s) ----
 (0008, 0100) Code Value SH: '111028'
 (0008, 0102) Coding Scheme Designator SH: 'DCM'
 (0008, 0104) Code Meaning LO: 'Image Library'

 (0040, a050) Continuity Of Content CS: 'CONTINUOUS'
 (0040, a730) Content Sequence 0 item(s) ----

 (0040, a010) Relationship Type CS: 'CONTAINS'
 (0040, a040) Value Type CS: 'CONTAINER'
 (0040, a043) Concept Name Code Sequence 1 item(s) ----
 (0008, 0100) Code Value SH: '126010'
 (0008, 0102) Coding Scheme Designator SH: 'DCM'
 (0008, 0104) Code Meaning LO: 'Imaging Measurements'

 (0040, a050) Continuity Of Content CS: 'CONTINUOUS'
 (0040, a730) Content Sequence 138 item(s) ----
 (0040, a010) Relationship Type CS: 'CONTAINS'
 (0040, a040) Value Type CS: 'CONTAINER'
 (0040, a043) Concept Name Code Sequence 1 item(s) ----
 (0008, 0100) Code Value SH: '125007'
 (0008, 0102) Coding Scheme Designator SH: 'DCM'
 (0008, 0104) Code Meaning LO: 'Measurement Group'

 (0040, a050) Continuity Of Content CS: 'CONTINUOUS'
 (0040, a504) Content Template Sequence 1 item(s) ----

(0008, 0105) Mapping Resource CS: 'DCMR'
 (0040, db00) Template Identifier CS: '1410'

(0040, a730) Content Sequence 5 item(s) ----

(0040, a010) Relationship Type CS: 'HAS OBS CONTEXT'
 (0040, a040) Value Type CS: 'TEXT'
 (0040, a043) Concept Name Code Sequence 1 item(s) ----
 (0008, 0100) Code Value SH: '112039'
 (0008, 0102) Coding Scheme Designator SH: 'DCM'
 (0008, 0104) Code Meaning LO: 'Tracking Identifier'

(0040, a160) Text Value UT: '1'

(0040, a010) Relationship Type CS: 'HAS OBS CONTEXT'
 (0040, a040) Value Type CS: 'UIDREF'
 (0040, a043) Concept Name Code Sequence 1 item(s) ----
 (0008, 0100) Code Value SH: '112040'
 (0008, 0102) Coding Scheme Designator SH: 'DCM'
 (0008, 0104) Code Meaning LO: 'Tracking Unique Identifier'

(0040, a124) UID UI: 2.25.242296886590626926585392185865325279802

(0040, a010) Relationship Type CS: 'CONTAINS'
 (0040, a040) Value Type CS: 'CODE'
 (0040, a043) Concept Name Code Sequence 1 item(s) ----
 (0008, 0100) Code Value SH: '121071'
 (0008, 0102) Coding Scheme Designator SH: 'DCM'
 (0008, 0104) Code Meaning LO: 'Finding'

(0040, a168) Concept Code Sequence 1 item(s) ----
 (0008, 0100) Code Value SH: '47973001'
 (0008, 0102) Coding Scheme Designator SH: 'SCT'
 (0008, 0104) Code Meaning LO: 'Artifact'

(0040, a010) Relationship Type CS: 'HAS CONCEPT MOD'
 (0040, a040) Value Type CS: 'CODE'
 (0040, a043) Concept Name Code Sequence 1 item(s) ----
 (0008, 0100) Code Value SH: '363698007'
 (0008, 0102) Coding Scheme Designator SH: 'SCT'
 (0008, 0104) Code Meaning LO: 'Finding Site'

(0040, a168) Concept Code Sequence 1 item(s) ----
 (0008, 0100) Code Value SH: '47973001'
 (0008, 0102) Coding Scheme Designator SH: 'SCT'
 (0008, 0104) Code Meaning LO: 'Artifact'

(0040, a010) Relationship Type CS: 'CONTAINS'
 (0040, a040) Value Type CS: 'COORD'
 (0040, a043) Concept Name Code Sequence 1 item(s) ----
 (0008, 0100) Code Value SH: '111030'

(0008, 0102) Coding Scheme Designator SH: 'DCM'
(0008, 0104) Code Meaning LO: 'Image Region'

(0040, a730) Content Sequence 1 item(s) ----

(0008, 1199) Referenced SOP Sequence 1 item(s) ----

(0008, 1150) Referenced SOP Class UID UI: VL Whole Slide Microscopy Image Storage

(0008, 1155) Referenced SOP Instance UID UI: 2.25.2852436523387486548764868821770429897

(0040, a010) Relationship Type CS: 'SELECTED FROM'

(0040, a040) Value Type CS: 'IMAGE'

(0040, a043) Concept Name Code Sequence 1 item(s) ----

(0008, 0100) Code Value SH: '111040'

(0008, 0102) Coding Scheme Designator SH: 'DCM'

(0008, 0104) Code Meaning LO: 'Original Source'

(0048, 0301) Pixel Origin Interpretation CS: 'VOLUME'

(0070, 0022) Graphic Data FL: Array of 22 elements

(0070, 0023) Graphic Type CS: 'POLYLINE'

Appendix 3. Annotation in DICOM microscope simple bulk format

(0020, 0052) Frame of Reference UID UI: 2.25.93659340635838159055460714585227804858
 (006a, 0001) Annotation Coordinate Type CS: '3D'
 (006a, 0002) Annotation Group Sequence 1 item(s) ----
 (0040, a180) Annotation Group Number US: 1
 (0066, 0022) Double Point Coordinates Data OD: Array of 16752 elements
 (0066, 0040) Long Primitive Point Index List OL:
 b"\x01\x00\x00\x00\x17\x00\x00\x005\x00\x00\x00Q\x00\x00\x00\x85\x00\x00\x00\xc9\x00\x00\x00\x85\x01\x00\x00A\x02\x00\x00\x93\x02\x00\x00\xd5\x02\x00\x00M\x03\x00\x00m\x03\x00\x00\xad\x03\x00\x00\xaf\x04\x00\x00\xd5\x04\x00\x00a\x05\x00\x00\x91\x05\x00\x00\xef\x05\x00\x00i\x06\x00\x00?\x07\x00\x00\xd5\x07\x00\x00\xf3\x07\x00\x00'
 (0066, 0121) Measurements Sequence 0 item(s) ----
 (006a, 0003) Annotation Group UID UI: 2.25.253666707808141408290541889456092775414
 (006a, 0005) Annotation Group Label LO: 'Epidermis'
 (006a, 0006) Annotation Group Description UT: 'Normal skin'
 (006a, 0007) Annotation Group Generation Type CS: 'MANUAL'
 (006a, 0009) Annotation Property Category Code Sequence 1 item(s) ----
 (0008, 0100) Code Value SH: '85756007'
 (0008, 0102) Coding Scheme Designator SH: 'SCT'
 (0008, 0104) Code Meaning LO: 'Tissue'

 (006a, 000a) Annotation Property Type Code Sequence 1 item(s) ----
 (0008, 0100) Code Value SH: '84640000'
 (0008, 0102) Coding Scheme Designator SH: 'SCT'
 (0008, 0104) Code Meaning LO: 'Nucleus'

 (006a, 000c) Number of Annotations UL: 22
 (006a, 000d) Annotation Applies to All Optical P CS: 'NO'
 (006a, 000e) Referenced Optical Path Identifier SH: ''
 (006a, 000f) Annotation Applies to All Z Planes CS: 'NO'
 (006a, 0010) Common Z Coordinate Value FD: None
 (0070, 0023) Graphic Type CS: 'POLYGON'

 (006a, 000c) Number of Annotations UL: 1
 (006a, 000d) Annotation Applies to All Optical P CS: 'NO'
 (006a, 000e) Referenced Optical Path Identifier SH: ''
 (006a, 000f) Annotation Applies to All Z Planes CS: 'NO'
 (006a, 0010) Common Z Coordinate Value FD: None
 (0070, 0023) Graphic Type CS: 'POLYGON'
